

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Том 1, Выпуск 4, 31 Декабря
TYPES OF CLOUD TECHNOLOGY

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ANNOTATION

This article details the creation of cloud technologies, the evolution process, and more. In addition, the advantages and disadvantages of using cloud technologies are analyzed.

Key words: : information technology, server services, Internet, cloud technology, cloud computing, personal computer, infrastructure.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past decade, the telecommunications industry has taken an important place in ensuring the growth of labor productivity and introducing new technologies. In the future, in various sectors of the national economy and economy, the basic infrastructure - e-commerce or the Internet will be used in the desired amount, and the wide-ranging introduction of various opportunities, this sector will encourage the formation of a new economy and the structure of the economy. It is undoubtedly becoming an important phenomenon as a catalyst for radical change. In the era of rapid development of information technologies, the role of software is very important. A personal computer must meet the minimum system requirements for the program to work properly. The Internet was modernized and server equipment was developed. At the same time, there was an idea to combine computing systems and use it as a single resource in using the program. Since 2008 (Cloud technology), the word "Cloud technology" has spread widely around the world. At first glance, "Cloud technologies" seem incomprehensible: this model allows quick, convenient, efficient use of a system (servers, applications, storage systems and services) [1].

Main. Not all clouds are the same, and one type of cloud computing is not right for everyone. Various models, types and services have emerged to offer the right solution to people's needs. There are three ways to deploy cloud services: Public, private, private cloud, or hybrid cloud.

Public clouds are owned and managed by third-party cloud service providers, such as servers and Internet storage. Microsoft Azure is an example of a public cloud. With public cloud, all hardware, software, and other supporting infrastructure are managed by the cloud provider. Users can access these services and manage their accounts using a web browser.

A private cloud refers to cloud computing resources used only by a single enterprise or organization. A private cloud can physically exist in a company's data

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center. Some companies also pay third-party service providers to host their private cloud. A private cloud is where services and infrastructure are stored on a private network.

In the development of mobile applications, cloud technology combines public and private clouds connected by technology that allows the mutual sharing of data and applications. By allowing data and applications to move between private and public clouds, a hybrid cloud gives businesses greater flexibility, additional deployment options, and helps optimize existing infrastructure, security, and compliance. Currently, the following types of clouds are distinguished:

1. Private clouds (private), which serve one organization, support it or are supported by a third-party company and are located on the territory of the organization or outside it. Subscribers are corporate offices and divisions, business partners, suppliers of raw materials, sellers, production chain participants and other organizations. Protected by the firewall, do not go outside the closed internal network, a high level of protection is provided;

2. Group clouds (community) distributed among several organizations united by common interests (service and location do not differ in private clouds);

3. Public or community clouds (public) provided to organizations or individuals based on the cloud provider's infrastructure. Any company and individual user can subscribe to the offered services. They offer an easy and inexpensive way to store and host websites or databases, and large-scale capabilities not available in other solutions;

4. Hybrid clouds combine the above in any combination, such as providing open and transparent services. allows using less hardware resources than required from the hardware capabilities allocated to one consumer, and due to the automation of modification procedures, resource allocation is significantly reduced. From the consumer's point of view, these features enable high service availability and low risk of downtime, and rapid scalability due to the flexibility of the computer system without the need to build, maintain, or upgrade a PC infrastructure. Ease of access and universality ensure the wide availability of services at scale. The convenience and universality of access is ensured by the wide availability of services and the support of various classes of terminal devices (personal computers, mobile phones, Internet tablets).

CONCLUSION

Using cloud technologies, computer system resources are protected based on innovative technologies of "collective intelligence". Antivirus servers can use data

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from Panda antivirus products from millions of users around the world to automatically detect and classify new types of malware that appear every day.

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